

Kinetics of Bromate--Oxalic Acid Reaction

CH. SANJEEVA REDDY and E. V. SUNDARAM*

Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009

Manuscript received 17 June 1986, revised 11 May 1987, accepted 11 August 1987

The oxidation of oxalic acid by Br(v) in acid medium unmixed by any competing or faster oxidation by any generated molecular bromine is studied in the presence of mercury(II), a bromo-complex forming metal ion, and reported. The reaction follows the rate law,

$$(-d[\text{Br}(v)]/dt) = \{kK_9 K_{10} + kK_{11} K_9 K_9 K_{a1}\} [\text{Br}(v)] [\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4] [\text{acid}]$$

A proposed mechanism involves a slow rate-determining formation of an oxaly-bromate ester followed by a fast decomposition to the products.

THE potentials¹ show that bromine in basic solutions (Ib) can disproportionate spontaneously to BrO⁻ and Br⁻ as Br₂ itself can disproportionate to Br⁻ and BrO₃⁻. However, in acidic

(Ia)

(Ib)

solutions (Ia) bromine doesn't disproportionate, and in fact it accumulates (1).

Most of the early investigations of the oxidation of organic substrates by bromate are essentially oxidations by bromine liberated by a reaction between Br(v) and the product Br⁻ ion. But our interest in these oxidations stemmed from a desire to study the direct oxidation of organic substrate by Br(v) in acid medium unmixed by any competing or faster oxidation by generated molecular bromine. This communication reports the results of such an investigation with oxalic acid as the substrate.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Distilled acetic acid (AnalaR) and conductivity water were used as solvents. All solutions were stored in the dark. The experiments were conducted under nitrogen and subdued light. Hypobromous acid was always prepared afresh². The reactions

were followed iodometrically for over three half-lives. The reproducibility of *k* was within ± 3%.

Results and Discussion

Varying proportions of bromate and oxalic acid solutions in the presence of acid and mercury(II), a bromide removing ion, were mixed and unreacted bromate or oxalic acid were estimated. Values of Δ[oxalic acid]/Δ[bromate] suggest the overall reaction (2),

In the absence of bromo-complex-forming metal ion the overall stoichiometry (3),

is obtained when elementary bromine was scrubbed³ from the solution by a stream of hydrogen gas. However, the same 3 : 1 stoichiometry (2) was obtained when Br₂ was not scrubbed from the solutions.

Certain peculiarities were observed while determining the order of the reaction with respect to Br(v). The reaction data could be fitted into a first order plot which shows that the reaction is indeed composed of two first order reaction. The first, comparatively slower one, being superseded after a particular stage by a faster reaction. During the oxidation (after about 15% of the reaction), the solution became yellow ($\lambda_{max} = 393 \text{ nm}$) presumably due to the liberation of Br₂ by an interaction between the unreacted bromate and the product Br⁻ ion. The faster one *viz.* the second step is mainly composed of molecular bromine oxidation with a much slower competing reaction by Br(v). The slower reaction is mainly a Br(v) oxidation and could be explained as follows. The second order rate constant for bromine oxidation of oxalic acid is close

to the rate constant for the second part of the bromate oxidation (Table 1). Initial addition of KBr completely suppresses the first part of the reaction and the reaction then follows simple first order kinetics right from the beginning. The rate constants again are nearly the same as those obtained for the second stage of the reaction or for the Br₂ oxidation under identical conditions.

TABLE 1—KINETICS OF BROMATE/BROMINE—OXALIC ACID REACTION AT 20±0.1°

[(COOH)₂]=0.01 M, [BrO₃⁻]/[Br₂]=0.001 M, [H₂SO₄]=1.0 M, HOAc-H₂O=10-90% (v/v)

Reaction*	k' (× 10 ⁴ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)		
	First stage	Second stage	Br ₂ -oxidation
1	9.60	31.4	—
2	—	32.7	—
3	—	—	34.6
4	9.59	—	—

* (1) Br(v)-oxalic acid, (2) Br(v)-oxalic acid in presence of added KBr (0.005 M), (3) bromine-oxalic acid, (4) Br(v)-oxalic acid in presence of added mercuric acetate (0.005 M).

A total suppression of the second stage of the reaction, with only the slower first part being observed from the beginning to over three half-lives, can be achieved by the initial addition of mercury(II) a bromo-complex-forming metal ion.

In the presence of mercuric acetate, Br⁻ ions formed in bromate-oxalic acid reaction, react with mercury(II) producing stable mercury(II)bromo-complexes⁴ (equilms. 4-7). Since bromide ions bound in the complex do not react with bromate, bromide ions accumulate in the presence of mercury(II).

Different concentrations of added mercuric acetate over a fifty-fold range do not affect the rate constants. Therefore, it can be taken for certain that in the Br(v)-oxalic acid system, mercury(II) behaves only as bromo-complex forming metal ion and its effect on the system is displayed by its complex-forming ability.

In the presence of mercury(II), at constant [H⁺] with the [substrate] in excess, the plot of log initial rate vs log [bromate]₀ is linear with a slope of one (Fig 1A), and the pseudo-first order rate constants were independent of [bromate]₀, indicating first order dependence of rate on [Br(v)]. Plot of log k_{obs} vs log [oxalic acid]₀ is linear with a slope of unity (Fig. 1B) and k_{obs}⁻¹ vs [oxalic acid]₀⁻¹ plot is

Fig. 1. [A] Plot of log₁₀ (initial rate) against log₁₀ [bromate]₀ at 30°, 30-70% (v/v), HOAc-H₂O, [H₂SO₄]=1.0 M and [H₂C₂O₄]=0.01 M; [B] plot of log₁₀ k_{obs} vs log [oxalic acid]₀ and [C] plot of 1/k_{obs} vs 1/[oxalic acid]₀, [BrO₃⁻]=0.001 M and other conditions as in (A).

linear passing through origin indicating a first order dependence on [substrate]. The k_{obs} values increase with the increase in acid (H₂SO₄/HClO₄, Table 2) concentration, and a plot of log k_{obs} vs log [acid] is linear with a slope of one.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF [ACID] ON THE RATE OF REACTION*

[Acid]/ M	k' (× 10 ⁴ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)					
	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	4.5	5.0
H ₂ SO ₄	8.77	16.35	23.03	31.75	37.53	40.85
HClO ₄	5.82	10.91	16.59	21.08	25.51	30.62

* [Hg(OAc)₂]=0.005 M, Temp. = 30°, HOAc-H₂O = 30-70% (v/v), other conditions as in Table 1.

TABLE 3—ACETIC ACID VARIATION IN BROMATE—OXALIC ACID REACTION

HOAc-H ₂ O (% v/v)	10-90 (69.70) ^a	20-80 (62.04) ^a	30-70 (55.59) ^a	40-60 (48.53) ^a	50-50 (41.48) ^a	60-40 (34.37) ^a
k' (× 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	3.49	5.37	8.77	14.76	24.75	59.85

*[H₂SO₄] = 1.0 M, other conditions as in Table 2.

^aDielectric constant of the media calculated by an approximate validity method at 30°.

An investigation of reaction rates at different proportions of acetic acid and water shows that increase in the percentage of acetic acid enhances the reaction rates (Table 3).

The activation parameters evaluated from runs at five different temperatures (20–50°) are $\Delta H^\ddagger = 20.52$ (in HClO₄ medium, 20.75) ± 0.3 kcal mol⁻¹, $-\Delta S^\ddagger = 7.5$ (4.7) ± 0.05 e.u., $\Delta G^\ddagger = 20.39$ (20.84) ± 0.2 kcal mol⁻¹, and $pZ = 2.1 \times 10^{11}$ (1.5×10^{11}) dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ at 30° and 30% acetic acid.

Oxalic acid is a dibasic acid with dissociation constants, $K_{a1} = 5.90 \times 10^{-2}$ mol⁻¹ and $K_{a2} = 6.40 \times 10^{-5}$ mol⁻¹ at 30°. In view of the low value of the second dissociation constant, oxalic acid exists in solution only as H₂C₂O₄ and HC₂O₄⁻. It can be shown that in solutions containing the total [oxalic acid] equal to 0.06 M, the concentrations of HC₂O₄⁻ is about 0.037 M and that of H₂C₂O₄ is about 0.023 M. It is therefore apparent that oxalic acid exists both as HC₂O₄⁻ and H₂C₂O₄ in appreciable portions.

On the basis of the above experimental findings, a mechanism for the Br(v)-oxalic acid reaction can be proposed (8 to 15),

Both HBrO₃ and H₂BrO₃⁺ are the probable active oxidant species with protonation constants, 0.50 l mol⁻¹ and 0.21 l² mol⁻², respectively⁸⁻⁹.

The second alternative step (13) that can also explain the observed data is that the bromate ester formed in steps (10) and (11) may also react with the proximate carboxylic acid group to form a cyclic ester which subsequently decomposes to products. Kinetically it is not possible to distinguish between these two steps (12 and 13).

The subsequent stage of the reaction of Br(III) to the final bromide ion can proceed by any one of the pathways. One such pathway involving stepwise two-electron transfer is

The hypobromous acid oxidation of oxalic acid has also been studied and observed that it follows third order, being first order in [H⁺], [oxalic acid] and [Br(I)]. The rates of these reactions are very fast and is approximately 47 times faster than Br(v) oxidations.

Although intermediate species of the type Br(IV) can also be proposed⁹ but the oxalic acid-bromate reaction failed to induce polymerisation or acrylonitrile or acrylamide, ruling out the possibility of one-electron oxidation steps giving rise to free radicals.

The rate law based on the mechanism is

$$-d[\text{Br}(v)]/dt = \{kK_8K_{10} + kK_{11}K_9K_{a1}\} [\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4] [\text{BrO}_3^-] [\text{H}^+] \quad (16)$$

The proposed mechanism is also supported by the observed rate law. This is further corroborated by the solvent influence on the reaction rate. The intermediate ester is less polar than the reactants due to dispersal of charge, hence decreasing polarity of the medium is expected to stabilise the

bromate ester in preference to the reactants, thereby enhancing the rate. Such a solvent influence has actually been observed.

References

1. W. M. LATIMER, "Oxidation Potentials", 2nd. ed., Prentice-Hall, New York, 1952.
2. M. K. REDDY, CH. S. REDDY and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Tetrahedron*, 1985, 41, 3071.
3. Z. NOSZTICZIUS and J. BODISS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 101, 3177.
4. E. KOROS, M. VARGA and L. GYORGYI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, 88, 4116; 1985, 89, 1019.
5. CH. S. REDDY and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1983, 15, 307.
6. CH. S. REDDY and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1983, 264, 737.
7. CH. S. REDDY and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Gazz. Chem. Ital.*, 1983, 113, 177.
8. CH. S. REDDY and E. V. SUNDARAM, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1987, 32, 183.
9. R. M. NOYES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 102, 4644.